

Synthesis of some biologically important hydrazone and azomethine compounds

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Abstract : 2-(4'-Sulphonamoylphenyl)hydrazonoindane-1,3-diones (**1a-e**) were synthesized by coupling indane-1,3-dione with diazotized sulphonamides. 3-(4'-Sulphonamoylphenyl) azomethineindoles (**2a-e**) and 3-(aminobenzothiazolyl) azomethineindole (**3**) were synthesised by refluxing indole-3-carboxaldehyde with sulfonamide derivatives and 3-aminobenzothiazole, respectively.

Keywords : Azomethine, biological activities.

Biological activity of sulphonamide is well known¹. Sulphonamide azomethine derivatives (containing CH=N group) have wide medical applications² and they have also found use in synthesis of polyesters³. Metal complexes of azomethines have been extensively synthesized due to their preparative accessibility, diversity, structural variability and industrial and biological applications⁴. Aminobenzothiazole azomethine derivatives have been of great importance due to their synthetic flexibility and biological activity of their metal complexes⁵.

Experimental

All m.ps. were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. UV-visible spectra were recorded on ELICO SL159 UV-visible spectrophotometer, IR spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 883 spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra on a Varian instrument using TMS as internal standard in DMSO-*d*₆. Compounds were routinely checked for purity on silica gel G plates.

2-(4'-Sulphonamoylphenyl)hydrazonoindane-1,3-diones (**1a-e**) :

Sulphanilamide (0.01 mol) was dissolved in mixture of conc. HCl (5 ml) and water (5 ml) and cooled to 0 °C in an ice bath. To this, pre-cooled solution of sodium nitrite (0.69 g, 0.01 mol) was added dropwise with constant stirring and maintaining temperature 0-5 °C. Diazonium salt so formed was filtered into cold solution of indane-1,3-dione (0.01 mol) in ethanol. The resultant compound (**1a**) was filtered and washed repeatedly with water and crystallized from ethanol, yield (69%), m.p. 158 °C; λ_{max} 378 nm; ν_{max} 1630 (C=N), 1575 (NH-N=C), 3240 (NH₂SO₂), 3053 (NH stretching), 1135 (SO₂) and 760

Scheme 1

cm⁻¹ (substituted phenyl); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 11.23 (s, NH), 7.13-7.16 (8H, m, ArH). Similarly other compounds were synthesized (yields 60-69%) : **1b**, m.p. 230 °C; **1c**, 240 °C, **1d**, 166 °C, **1e**, 221 °C (Scheme 1).

3-(4'-Sulphonamoylphenyl)azomethineindoles (**2a-e**) :

Sulphanilamide (0.01) was dissolved in absolute ethanol (15 ml). To this, solution of indole-3-carboxaldehyde (0.01 mol) in ethanol containing 2-3 drops of acetic acid was added. Solution mixture was refluxed for 4-5 h with

Scheme 2

constant stirring. Then, cooled the solution in an ice bath and the resultant solid (2a) was separated and washed repeatedly with water and crystallized from ethanol, yield (60%), m.p. 95 °C; λ_{\max} 218, 260, 289 and 325 nm; ν_{\max} 1634 (C=N), 3065 (NH stretching) and 758 cm^{-1} (substituted phenyl); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6) δ 7.8 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.1 (1H, m, NH) and 6.90–6.95 (8H, m, ArH). Similarly other compounds were synthesized (yields 55–60%) : **2b**, m.p. 128 °C, **2c**, 98 °C; **2d**, 141 °C; **2e**, 92 °C (Scheme 2).

3-(Benzothiazolyl)azomethineindole (3) :

2-Aminobenzothiazole (0.01 mol) was dissolved in

ethanol (15 ml). To this, solution of indole-3-carboxaldehyde (0.01 mol) in ethanol with 2–3 drops of acetic acid was added. Solution mixture was refluxed for 3–4 h with constant stirring. After that the solution was cooled in an ice bath and resultant solid (**3**) was separated and washed repeatedly with water and crystallized from ethanol, yield (64%), m.p. 82 °C; λ_{\max} 285 and 365 nm; ν_{\max} 1620 cm^{-1} (C=N); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6) δ 7.8 (1H, s, CH=N) and 6.85 (8H, m, ArH) (Scheme 2).

Biological activities :

The antimicrobial activities of the synthesized compounds were investigated against several representative pathogenic bacteria and fungi. Four microbial strains, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus* as bacteria and *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans* as fungi were used for antimicrobial assay. Ampicillin trihydrate and clotrimazole were also screened under similar conditions as reference antibacterial and antifungal drug, respectively. The results of antibacterial and antifungal activity of hydrazono and azomethine compounds are incorporated in Table 1. All the synthesized compounds exhibit an antimicrobial potency on both bacteria and fungi as compound to reference drugs within a MIC range of 1–15 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Compounds **3c**, **3d**, **3e** showed maximum activity against *Candida albicans* compound **3** was highly active against *Aspergillus niger*. Compounds **2c** and **2d** displayed maximum activity against **2b** and **2c**. All other compounds were moderately active against the bacteria and fungi.

Table 1. Antibacterial and antifungal activity of hydrazono and azomethine compounds

Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Zone of inhibition (mm)											
	<i>B. subtilis</i>			<i>S. aureus</i>			<i>A. niger</i>			<i>C. albicans</i>		
	1	10	15	1	10	15	1	10	15	1	10	15
Compd.												
1a	5	9	11	4	10	12	1.5	8	11	2.5	8	10.5
1b	8.5	16	18.5	6	14	17	2	8.5	12	3.5	7.5	13
1c	8	15.5	17	5.5	12	16.5	2	7.5	11.5	3	7	11.5
1d	6.5	13	15.5	7	16.5	20	2.5	9	13	3.5	8	12
1e	7	14	16	7.5	17	21.5	2.5	10	14.5	3.5	8	12.5
2a	3	5	9	–	6	9	3	11	15	3	9.5	13
2b	2.5	6	9.5	3	6.5	10	3	10.5	14	3.5	11	15
2c	2.5	5.5	10	3	7	10.5	2.5	10	13	4	12.5	16
2d	2	5	10	3.5	8	12	2	9	12.5	4.5	14	17.5
2e	2	4.5	9	3	7	11	2	8.5	12	5	14.5	18
3	–	3.5	8	–	5.5	9	4	14.5	19	4	13.5	17

Note

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